

Step 2. Playlist selection task

The moderator asks the participant to log out from Spotify in their browser, if logged in.

Task Description

In this task, you will receive several options for playlists. On each page, please select your favorite playlist. We ask you to **think aloud** while you are going through the task, and try to say everything that goes through your mind.

Listening to songs: by clicking the play button next to a song, you can listen to it. You can pause the song by clicking again. Once you've listened to a song, a message will appear. If you want to re-listen, you can close the message by clicking the cross and press play again.

Selecting a playlist: there will be four rounds and in each round you can select a playlist by clicking on one of the songs in a playlist or the area next to it. You can confirm your choice by clicking the arrow at the bottom of the page. There is no right or wrong choice, it is all about your choice.

[I Understand](#)

Think Aloud Practice

Please listen to this song preview and tell us what you think. You don't need to listen to the full preview.

Proceed

(arrow appears once the participant selects a playlist)

Thank You!

Thank you for choosing your favorite playlists!

On the next pages, we will show all playlists again, but this time, we have added a brief description of what type of songs are in each playlist. You have the possibility to modify your initial selection, or keep it as is.

Again, we ask you to please **think aloud** while you are going through the task, and try to say everything that goes through your mind.

PROCEED

Thank You!

Thank you for your selection. The moderator will now ask you some questions.

INTERVIEW FINISHED